

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF DESIGN COMPETENCE OF
FUTURE TEACHERS OF DRAWING SCIENCE USING INTERACTIVE
EDUCATIONAL METHODS

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Annotation: *This article provides informative information about the methodology of developing the project competence of future drawing teachers by means of interactive teaching methods. It was written based on the results of research conducted by scientists and teachers on the development of spatial imagination and thinking of future teachers, as well as project competence.*

Keywords: *drawing, construction, modeling, inert method, spatial imagination, spatial thinking, methodical system.*

Аннотация: *Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak chizmachilik fani o'qituvchilarining loyihalash kompetentligini interfaol ta'lim metodlari vositasida rivojlantirish metodikasi haqida asosli ma'lumotlar berilgan. U pedagog-olimlar tomonidan bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning fazoviy tasavvuri va tafakkurini hamda loyihalash kompetentligini rivojlantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalari asosida yozilgan.*

Калит so'zlar: *chizmachilik, loyihalash, kompetentlik, interfaol metod, fazoviy tasavvur, fazoviy tafakkur, metodik tizim.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье дана содержательная информация о методике развития проектной компетентности будущих учителей рисования средствами интерактивных методов обучения. Он был написан на основе результатов исследований, проведенных учеными-педагогами по развитию пространственного воображения и мышления будущих учителей, а также проектной компетентности.*

Ключевые слова: *черчения, конструирование, моделирование, инертный метод, пространственное воображение, пространственное мышление, методическая система.*

Interactive educational methods are a complex of actions aimed at mutual exchange of views, replenishment of mutual thoughts, nonverbal and verbal interaction. Intellectual actions built on the basis of interaction in the application of interactive techniques are not only limited to the performance of the function of influence or motivation, but can also perform the functions of directing the subjects of cooperation in creative search, creating theoretical-reasoning, which contributes to the discovery(discovery) of an unknown situation.

In mastering the content of education, the level of knowledge of students, the level of mastering, the source of education, in accordance with and in accordance with didactic functions, the following interactive methods are used: visual method of teaching; method of independent work; problematic-the method of evristik modeling; methods of scientific research; problematic-the searchable and reproductive methods of teaching; inductive and deductive methods.

The methods include the following groups:

Methods of the first group: *methods of receiving educational information through hearing (oral techniques: Story, Lecture, conversation, etc.).*

Methods of the second group: *methods of visual transmission and visual perception of educational information (visual method, visual demonstration, etc.).*

Methods of the third group: *providing educational information through practical labor movements (practical methods, exercises, laboratory work, drawing up programs, solving exercises and issues, as well as Test assignments, labor movements, etc.).*

Different strategies are used in lesson systems based on interactive techniques. Bunda gives students the opportunity to use secret methods (books, conjectures, etc.) use is not prohibited, on the contrary, the use of such methods is encouraged.

Currently, there is an increasing interest in the use of interactive techniques in the educational process. Bunda said that basically until now, when students are trained to acquire ready-made knowledge, interactive techniques teach them to search for the knowledge they possess, independently study, analyze, and, if possible, draw conclusions themselves. The teacher in this process creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition and upbringing of knowledge of the individual and at the same time performs the function of stewardship, directing.

Interaktiv methods-are based on collective thinking and are methods of pedagogical influence, are a component of the content of Education. The peculiarity of these techniques is that they are carried out only through the joint activities of both the educator and the student. Drawing teacher is also required to have knowledge of modern technologies and skills of appropriate use of them in his professional activity.

The correct choice of teaching methods in the teaching of drawing science ensures the interrelation between the goal and the result. Therefore, OTM educators are required to pay special attention to the correct choice of them. The correct selection of educational methods in the teaching of drawing science is carried out on the basis of the following: general objectives of teaching; specific aspects and characteristics of a particular educational science; goals, tasks intended for the teaching of the subject, as well as the content of the educational material intended for each individual training; the volume of time allocated for the; the level of preparation of students, psychological and physiological indicators; the availability of educational, technical and technological equipment (educational equipment, pointing weapons, technical, computer and other material means) of the educational process; the level of preparation and personal qualities of the educator [1].

Particular attention should be paid to the selection of educational methods in the organization of training sessions, especially practical ones, in the development of the competence of the design of teachers of the future drawing science at the university. The correct choice of teaching methods guarantees the achievement of the following results: the formation of interest and motivation in the thorough mastering of the fundamentals of engineering graphic Sciences in students; the increase in their educational and cognitive activity; ensuring that students have independent, critical and creative thinking skills; improve the quality of teaching students the fundamentals of engineering graphics science; improve the effectiveness of teaching engineering graphics science.

In the course of carrying out the study, attention was paid to the effective use of interactive techniques in lectures and practical classes. Bunda chose interactive techniques that were able to provide the expected result, taking into account their characteristic features, primarily for lectures and practical classes [2]. That is:

I. Selected Interpol techniques for theoretical training:

1. To determine the extent to which students have mastered theoretical knowledge of the subject under the module "Forty" on the basis of the method "definition of concepts".

Working paper

№	Concepts	Their description
1.	Crimea	
2.	The difference between forty and cross-section	
3.	Simple face	
4.	Complex side	

Execution of the task (sample)

№	Concepts	Their description
1.	Crimea	It is said that the inconspicuous internal structure of the detail is forty to the fact that the figure is cut out with one or several planes.
2.	The difference between forty and cross-section	In the foreground, the place where the detail is cut with a plane, and the (visible) parts located behind the cutting plane are also indicated by the addition. In the cut, only the area of the detail cut by plane is indicated by itself.
3.	Simple face	If it is possible to indicate the internal structure of the detail through a single plane, then such a forty is considered simple.

4.	Complex side	When determining the internal manifestations of the detail, two or more cutting planes are applied, then a complex Forty is formed.
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2. **“I know. I want to know. To determine whether students have mastered theoretical knowledge of the subject under the” axonometric projections “module based on the method” I learned ” (BBB).**

Working paper

I know	I want to know	I found out

Топшириқнинг бажарилиши (намуна)

I know	I want to know	I found out
1. Axonometry soy. 2. Axonometry arrows. 3. Rectangularisometry. 4. Rectangular dimetry.	1. Axonometry plane. 2. Cofficients of change on axonometric arrows. 3. Axonometric massshtab. 4. The main theorem of axonometry. 5. Isometry with a bevel angle. 6. Oblique angle dimetry. 7. Technical picture.	1. Axonometry plane. 2. Cofficients of change on axonometric arrows. 3. Axonometric massshtab. 4. The main theorem of axonometry. 5. Isometry with a bevel angle. 6. Oblique angle dimetry. 7. Technical picture.

II. Interactive techniques selected for practical training:

1. Blis game - "I am the organizer of Jif" method. In Table 1, in the style of "I am a jif organizer", students were asked to determine the stage of processing an issue related to proxying drawing. At the first stage, each student participates and is evaluated individually. In the second stage, the group is divided into small groups by at least 4 people and is evaluated. And at the end of the training, the teacher evaluates each student individually, as well as the groups, indicating the inadequacies allowed.

From the application of the above interactive techniques in the lessons, the aim is to provide students with theoretical knowledge, as well as to develop their practical skills and design competency. Because gaming technologies are distinguished from other styles by the fact that they teach the student to work with the team, free thinking, and not every student is overlooked. Also, giving knowledge to the teacher is also easy to evaluate.

The main useful aspect of this game Method to the student is that the student learns to work in an orderly and phased manner not on white paper, but fantastically, that is, in his spatial imagination, the subjects given from the pro-choice drawing.

In the context of the issue presented in Table 1, it is stated that “on the basis of the two views given in detail, it is necessary to find the third view, Build axonometric

projection, perform forty on orthogonal and axonometric projections” and determine its planned algorithm [3].

Table 1

	Subject content	Individual assessment	Single error	Group price	And the mistake	Correct answer
	Two views of the detail can be placed on the drawing paper and the third view can be found					
	In axonometric proection, Forty is performed					
	Dimensions are laid out in detail drawings					
	Axonometric type of projection is selected					
	Detailed axonometry will be built					
	Drawing paper draw a frame line, the main writing role is allocated					
	At the orthogonal projection, Forty is performed					

2. Evaluation of students ' level of knowledge, skills and competency using keys-Stadi technology.

Description of keys

Before solving a graphical issue, it is necessary to understand its condition and determine the resolution sequence. It is necessary to design the given detail through the points of the socket, which are marked on it, to form a new detail, it is possible to draw several samples (model) of the detail that is being projected from the new one on the whiteboard [4].

Keys assignment and question

Figure 1, a) given scheme of sorting (taqsimlash) adjustment in Fig. So design the detail so that the bubbles go right, Goh fall into the left hole and go out.

Sources for use:

1. Turaev X. "Graphic fundamentals of developing design compitence for future drawing science teachers". - What?: Monograph. "LESSON PRESS". 2021 y. 47-48 B.

Figure 1

Methodical instructions for students:

When solving such issues, the teacher first explains the meaning of the word “sort” in the issue assignment.

Information is given about the task of performing the work of the given object.

A few examples of the detail that is being projected for the sorting (taqsimlash) device are shown in the drawing.

The process of solving the keys

Students complete the assignment and provide a solution.

Teacher's solution

A T-shaped barrier should be installed in the sorting device chamber. Its geometrical shape will depend on the cross-section of the tarnovs. If the cross-section is in the form of a square, then the fixture is prepared as in figure 1, e) if there is a circle, as in Figure 1, d) if there is a circle.

The transition of the Sharps to the hole in the Goh chap is given in figure 1, b) the fall of the Goh to the hole on the right is given in figure 1, c).

This means that interactive techniques and technologies help to increase student learning activity. As a result, they carefully master the knowledge of the science of drawing. The acquired theoretical knowledge will enable the students to effectively organize professional activities as a future specialist. By improving the quality of educational activities using interactive methods and technologies in the teaching of drawing science subjects, the development of competency qualities of future drawing science teachers is achieved.

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